

Record of journal submissions

This document records all journal submissions of the study "Global Climate Trends in Seven Climatic Parameters: A Comparative Analysis Across 100 Locations" and its earlier version "A Global Peek at Climate Data Trends Since 1984", between October 2023 and May 2026. Several journals were approached over this period; the manuscript did not proceed to peer review in any of them. Three entries (15, 25, 36) were withdrawn due to open-access publication charges. Entry 6 is absent from the record for reasons no longer recalled. The right column lists the submission code and excerpts from the editor's email explaining the rejection. The list is published here as part of the Zenodo deposit, without comment beyond what the editor's letters themselves contain.

Initial manuscript:

A global peek at climate data trends since 1984

<i>Journal</i>	<i>Date of rejection</i>	<i>Rejection email excerpt</i>
1 Solar Energy	17.10.2023	SEJ-D-23-03128 The topic of the manuscript does not align well with the scope of this journal but may be suitable elsewhere. I am, therefore, returning the manuscript without further consideration.
2 Current Climate Change Reports	18.10.2023	Submission ID cb1a3da2-2d08-477e-8148-7a6617919a43 Regrettably, the above submission has been rejected for publication in Current Climate Change Reports.
3 Journal of Environmental Sciences	24.10.2023	JESC-D-23-03111 I regret to inform you that your manuscript will not be considered further by the journal for the reason below. The research results reported are too premature for publication. More work is needed to refine and deepen the results in your manuscript. Additionally, from our preliminary evaluation of your manuscript, we do not think this manuscript would be ranked in the top 10-15% of the manuscripts we receive and ultimately publish, even though we do not question the importance and usefulness of this work. We strive to make a decision in a timely manner, so that you may consider other venues for publishing your work without much delay.
4 Environmental Research	4.4.24	ER-24-4350 We have been checking your manuscript and I must communicate to you that your submission will not be sent for external review. Unfortunately, your submission has not reached the sufficient priority to be selected for publication in the journal. Please note that ER is currently receiving well above average submissions. As we receive much more manuscripts than those we can publish, we must prioritize the submissions that will be externally reviewed.
5 Climatic Change	12.11.23	CLIM-D-23-00958 Your paper examines correlations between pairs of climate variables at 100 locations around the world, over the period 1982-2022, based on data downloaded from the RETScreen software package. However, you do not attempt to explain the correlations (that is left for another paper), and so your paper does not present new scientific insights. As such your, paper will not be of broad interest to the readership of Climatic Change.
7 International Journal of Climatology	21.11.23	JOC-23-0729 Your manuscript has been denied publication in the International Journal of Climatology. We value your research, but we are afraid that the regression analysis of a short data period (1984 onwards) of annual means of different climate elements does not yield novel results likely to capture the interest of our readership.
8 Nature Climate Change	23.11.23	NCLIM-23112635 Regretfully, we cannot offer to consider it for publication. We receive many more papers than we can publish, which means we must

		<p>decline a substantial proportion of manuscripts without sending them to referees, so that they may be sent elsewhere without delay. Decisions of this kind are made by the editorial staff when it appears that, even if certified as being technically correct during peer review, there would not be a strong case for publication in Nature Climate Change. Among the considerations that arise at this stage are the immediacy of interest for the wider climate research community, the degree of advance provided, and the like.</p> <p>In this case we have no doubt that your study will be of interest to others in the same and related fields. However, we are not persuaded that your findings will be of sufficiently immediate interest to the broader climate change community to justify publication in Nature Climate Change.</p>
9 Weather, Climate, and Society	30.11.23	<p>WCAS-D-23-0141</p> <p>Returned by journal for amendments; withdrawn by author.</p> <p>Your Weather, Climate, and Society manuscript WCAS-D-23-0141 "A global peek at climate data trends since 1984" is being returned to you for the following reason(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -- Text must be set using a 12-point font, including the references. Please adjust the font size of your references. -- Figure and table elements should appear in a single column and without text wrap. Captions must appear immediately above or below figures and tables, not beside them. Please adjust Figures 4-20 so that the elements appear in a single column, with captions immediately beneath the figure images. -- The 2x2 matrices cannot be included as part of the caption text for Figures 4-20 I suggest incorporating these matrices into your figure images so they can appear as you intend. Alternatively you could set them as separate, individually numbered and captioned tables and reference them if needed. -- Each of your captioned tables and figures should be embedded in the body of the manuscript as close as possible to its first citation following a paragraph. Please move the tables from the end of your manuscript file and instead embed these elements near their first citations in the body text. Please see the Tables and Figures sections of our Formatting and Manuscript Components page for additional information. -- The Data and Software Availability Statement is a required manuscript element. Please include an Availability Statement after the body text and before the References. Include the section heading "Availability Statement". Full information regarding this requirement is available on our website.
10 Journal of Environmental Management	17.12.23	<p>JEMA-D-23-19960</p> <p>After carefully examining your manuscript, I am sorry to inform you that it cannot be further considered for publication in Journal of Environmental Management. Some factors entering into this decision include scope, depth of research work, originality, and adherence to journal guidelines.</p>
11 Building and Environment	21.12.23	<p>BAE-D-23-05766</p> <p>This manuscript is beyond the aims and scope of Building and Environment and is not suitable for the journal. I regret that Building and Environment could not publish your paper.</p>
12 Climate & Development	Submitted 22.12.23 Withdrawn 23.3.24	<p>232262370</p> <p>By the author, 19.3.24</p> <p>Dear Taylor & Francis editors,</p> <p>It has been almost three months since I submitted my manuscript, and still I have no news on its status.</p> <p>Apparently the T&F editors are very busy, but time is precious to me and I wish to send my manuscript to another publisher.</p> <p>However, I feel trapped with Taylor & Francis as I might encounter problems if I have a parallel submission before officially terminating the current one.</p> <p>Could you please let me know how to escape from this stalemate?</p>

13 Regional Environmental Change	10.4.24	REEC-D-24-00308 We have completed the evaluation of your manuscript. Unfortunately we have concluded that we cannot consider it for further review or publication. Therefore we must reject it. In all honesty, I could not find the scientific problem your paper is trying to solve. Also, I do not think that your focus is about regional environmental change.
14 Climate Research	12.4.24	CR-2024-04-001 The Editors-in-Chief Dr. Semenov and Dr. Stenseth have now examined your manuscript and, unfortunately, do not consider it suitable for publication in this journal due to its lack of novelty and in depth analysis. They have therefore decided against sending your manuscript out for peer review. Thus, we regret to inform you that your manuscript cannot be considered further for publication in Climate Research. We hope that this rapid decision allows you to more quickly move forward with submission to another publication outlet.
15 <i>Journal of Climate</i>	22.5.24 <i>withdrawal</i>	JCLI-D-24-0271 <i>Withdrawn due to APC</i>
16 Energy Ecology and Environment	13.9.24	Submission ID e846e5a2-aad4-44a2-8754-7c2663d0250a Regrettably, your manuscript has been rejected for publication in Energy, Ecology and Environment due to insufficient contribution and technical standard.
17 Environmental and Ecological Statistics	26.9.24	Submission ID 0b7cc400-acdd-43db-b768-8b1491e38c16 Regrettably, your manuscript has been rejected for publication in Environmental and Ecological Statistics. The manuscript appears as a serious study, but it appears more as a technical report and its development is centered on very simple statistical tools of analysis. It would be better received in a more specialized journal for publication instead.
18 Journal of Environmental Engineering and Science	3.10.24	ENES-2024-133 I regret to inform you that your paper has been found unsuitable for <i>Journal of Environmental Engineering and Science</i> and unfortunately cannot be accepted for publication because it is out of the scope of the Journal.
19 International Journal of Environmental Research	8.10.24	IJER-D-24-01549 With regret, I must inform you that I have decided that your paper cannot be accepted for publication in the International Journal of Environmental Research
20 Energy and Climate Change	1.11.24	EGYCC-D-24-00253 After careful evaluation, our assessment is that your manuscript falls out of the scope of Energy and Climate Change and would be better suited for a journal focused on the technical aspects of climate change.
20 <i>Sustainability & Climate Change</i>		<i>not sent due to APC</i>
21 Global Environment	22.4.24	The article is great but not adapted to our history magazine. We have reached a decision regarding your submission to Global Environment, "A global peek at climate data trends since 1984". Our decision is to: Decline Submission
22 Urban Climate	22.4.24	UCLIM-D-25-01102 Thank you for submitting your manuscript to Urban Climate. I regret to inform you that your manuscript does not have the scientific significance required by this journal and we must therefore reject it. Although the problems being addressed are potentially of interest to our readership, your manuscript does not meet the required quality standards to be considered for publication. The research results reported are too premature for publication. More work is needed to substantiate the conclusions in your manuscript.
23 International Journal of Global Environmental Issues	Submitted 23.4.25	IJGENVI-263876 Withdrawn 2.7.25 due to delay in editor's response.

24 Environmental Engineering and Management Journal	9.7.25	<p>I have carefully examined your manuscript. With regret, I must inform you that your manuscript cannot be accepted or further considered for publication in the Environmental Engineering and Management Journal.</p> <p>The paper is not acceptable because the overall scientific content is too low for the <i>Environmental Engineering and Management Journal</i>. MOREOVER YOUR MANUSCRIPT DOESN'T FOLLOW OUR JOURNAL RULES AND GUIDELINES, WHICH IS THE FIRST RULE FOR ANY SUBMISSION.</p> <p>Rather than lengthening the decision process, we now reject some manuscripts without full peer-review when it appears unlikely that the paper can be accepted for publication by the peer-reviewers. In these conditions we cannot accept anymore a revised manuscript for consideration in our Journal.</p>
25 <i>International Journal of Ecosystems and Ecology Science</i>	28.7.25	<i>Withdrawn due to APC</i>
26 METU JFA		<p>First of all please accept our apologies for belated notification. We have reached a decision regarding your submission to METU Journal of the Faculty of Architecture, "A global peek at climate data trends since 1984".</p> <p>Our decision is to: Reject Submission</p> <p>Please find below the reviewer's and my comments. You will see that responses and advice are mostly against your paper. Therefore, considering the comments, the editorial board of METU JFA has decided that your manuscript cannot be accepted for publication.</p> <p><i>Reviewer's Comments:</i></p> <p>This manuscript provides an overview of global urban climate trends by examining the relationships between rising air temperatures and various other climatic and geophysical variables across 100 urban locations worldwide. Using NASA satellite data from 1984 to 2022, the study compares the trends of variables like solar radiation, precipitation, relative humidity, wind speed, and latitude to identify quantitative correlations.</p> <p>The research employs graphical analysis and linear regression to visualize these complex interrelationships, serving as a preliminary exploration to guide future, more in-depth studies on the dynamics of climate change.</p> <p>However, there are major clarity issues throughout the manuscript to improve the quality.</p> <p>First of all, the authors implied that the objective of this study is to conduct a comparative analysis of trends in major climatic parameters on a global scale, examining their interrelationships and exploring the influence of non-meteorological factors. However, I did not find any explanation for how these non-meteorological factors affect the meteorological variables physically. Trend analyses are shortly explained only by means of their statistical distribution rather than explaining why and/or how these parameters affect each other or how other factors (elevation, location, etc.) influence these trends.</p> <p>We already know behavior of air temperature or other parameters trend especially specific region in the world. I understand that the authors tried to give more information about out of more studied locations, however, this attempt does not go beyond a basic technical report since they do not give explanations "why". For example, the relation between wind speed and air temperature. Moreover, the given references seem incomplete sentences. For instance, if you take a look at the subsection 3.1.8 wind speed (on page 10) "Young and Ribal (2019) studied oceanic wind speed trends due to climate warming, while You et al. (2013) investigated the wind speed in Tibet after 1980." It is not clear what they found. Do these studies support what you find or</p>

		<p>not?</p> <p>If the authors' study had aimed to demonstrate the superiority of the NASA POWER dataset over other satellite- and station-based datasets, using only trend analysis to examine relationships with other datasets might have been meaningful. However, the absence of an accuracy analysis for this dataset raises questions about how well it represents the studied regions in question. I also wonder why the authors prefer to get data through the RETScreen Expert software package; it seems that it is also possible to get them from NASA. Could you please clarify?</p> <p>Considering all these, I believe the manuscript is far beyond the contribution to the literature in this form. Therefore, I must reject it for publication.</p> <p>There are other issues that the authors should be careful of if they want to improve the manuscript, in addition to providing more explanations and extra analyses.</p> <p>Only "climate change" takes place in the abstract out of the four keywords, which abstract should include these words. In Introduction section (on page 1) "Do these variables also exhibit distinct changes affected by the global warming, either in an upward or downward direction?" I just to the authors use increase/decrease instead of upward/downward.</p> <p>Figure captions should explain everything in the figure, including the legend. For example, the numbers on the right of the scatter plot Figure 4 (in all figures). Climate zones should be added to y-axis in figure 10 or as a legend.</p> <p>I believe that subsection information is not proper. Instead of Air Temperature Compared To ... It should be "Air temperature comparisons to meteorological/non-meteorological parameters" or anything that explains what the authors try to do in the subsection.</p> <p><i>Editor's Comments:</i></p> <p>I have reviewed the submitted manuscript; however, I must note at the outset that the paper does not appear to have a clear or direct connection to the field of climate change or climate policy. The analysis presented focuses primarily on statistical correlations between latitude, solar radiation, and meteorological parameters. While such an exercise may hold value within the scope of meteorological or statistical modeling studies, it does not engage with the established scientific frameworks or policy dimensions of climate change research.</p> <p>The manuscript does not refer to greenhouse gas emissions, emission scenarios, or the physical basis of global warming, nor does it situate its findings within the broader literature informed by IPCC assessments or other relevant global models. In its current form, the paper reads more as an isolated data exercise rather than a contribution to climate change science or policy understanding.</p> <p>Overall, I do not find the manuscript suitable for publication in a journal devoted to climate change research. The topic, as currently framed, may even risk creating conceptual confusion by implying a connection to climate change that the content does not substantiate.</p>
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Revised-renamed:

Using Public Tools for Global Climate Trend Analysis: A RETScreen and NASA POWER Case Study (1984–2022)

27 Journal of Building Engineering	28.11.25	JBE-D-25-18724 After careful evaluation, I regret to inform you that your manuscript does not fit within the scope of the journal, and I must therefore reject it.
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		While your results are of potential interest, the topic of your manuscript falls outside of the scope of this journal.
28 Sustainable Cities and Society	29.11.25	SCSI-D-25-13221 We have examined your manuscript carefully; however, we find that the topic and content of your work do not fit the scope of this journal. Therefore, we regret that we cannot consider your work further and suggest you submit it to another journal that can accommodate your work better.
29 Energy & Buildings	13.12.25	ENB-D-25-08217 After careful evaluation, I regret to inform you that your manuscript does not fit within the scope of the journal, and I must therefore reject it. While your results are of potential interest, the topic of your manuscript falls outside of the scope of this journal.
30 Building and Environment (attempt 2)	14.12.25	BAE-D-25-09403 Due to the large numbers of submissions to Building and Environment, we wish to give the priority to the most novel papers that deal with more advanced aspects, technologies or methodologies and that are expected to have a large impact in the field of building and environment. After a careful evaluation of your paper, we have decided to return your submission without review. Please understand that this decision has nothing to do with the technical content of the paper or its value to the archival literature. The decision reflects the best interests of the journal and its audience.
31 Applied Energy	16.12.25	I regret to inform you that after careful consideration and discussion with my editorial colleagues, your manuscript was not given a high priority rating during our initial assessment. We have decided not to send your paper for further review. As you may know, we decline a substantial proportion of manuscripts without sending them to referees, so that they may be sent elsewhere without delay. These editorial judgements are based on such considerations as significant, innovative, original research that advances the frontiers of science and applications.
32 Environmental Modelling and Software	13.3.26	ENVSOFT-D-26-00680 We apologize for the time it has taken to complete this process. We regret to inform you that based upon review, we are declining to send the manuscript out for further review.
33 Environmental Monitoring and Assessment	23.3.26	Submission ID de0024aa-85da-4865-a361-45ec9556176e. Regrettably, your manuscript has been rejected for publication in Environmental Monitoring and Assessment. An interesting paper, but this paper is not within our scope.
34 Theoretical and Applied Climatology	29.1.26	Submission ID b05fc583-5da4-4fd5-8d44-5d5480a861fc Following an assessment, our Editors have decided this journal is not a suitable publication for your article.
35 Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments	9.2.26	SETA-D-26-00902 However, after initial evaluation by the Editorial Office, the decision is to desk reject for the following reasons: * Textual similarity: There is too much textual similarity with previously published work, based on the results of the iThenticate CrossCheck report. This will need to be addressed—making sure you use your own words when citing other sources. For more information on proper crediting, acknowledgement and reuse of previously published work (including one's own work), please read this guide. (Note: SETA does not issue CrossRef reports to authors even if requested, as the responsibility to check and revise their work if plagiarism is unintentional or intentional lies solely and wholly with the author(s)). * Guide for Authors: The paper does not follow the requirements set out in the Guide for Authors. Please ensure your paper adheres to all the points listed in the Guide for Authors. * Content: The paper does not meet the Journal's standards for quality in terms of our content and structure requirements.

		<p>* Language: In its current state your manuscript does not meet the journal's required English standard requirements. Author(s) should get help from a colleague with better English, or alternatively a paid English language editing service of which there are many, could be arranged.</p> <p>* Scope: We have examined your manuscript carefully; however, we find that the topic and content of your work does not fit the current scope and needs of the journal.</p> <p><i>[apparently the editor's automatic search found similarities with my own text previously published in Academia in an early version.]</i></p>
36 Journal of Water & Climate Change	8.3.26	Abandoned due to APC
37 Journal of Environmental Management	1.3.26	<p>JEMA-D-26-04450</p> <p>After thorough consideration, we regret to inform you that we are unable to consider your manuscript for publication in this journal.</p> <p>Our decision is based on concerns regarding the overall quality of your manuscript. We receive a high volume of submissions and are committed to maintaining the highest standards in the field of environmental management. Unfortunately, your manuscript does not meet these standards in its current form. This may encompass various aspects such as the rigor of the methodology, clarity of presentation, depth of analysis, and the overall contribution to the field.</p>
38 Environmental Modelling & Software	18.12.25	<p>NVSOFT-D-25-03135</p> <p>We apologize for the time it has taken to complete this process. We regret to inform you that based upon review, we are declining to send the manuscript out for further review. As you may know, we receive more submissions than we can publish, which sometimes means we do not send out for review some high-quality manuscripts, so that they may be sent elsewhere without delay.</p>

Revised-renamed:

Global Climate Trends in Seven Climatic Parameters: A Comparative Analysis Across 100 Locations

39 International Journal of Climatology (attempt 2)		Submission prepared but not completed.
40 Atmosfera	2.5.26	<p>As a Chief Editor, I have carried out an initial, internal review of your submission to <i>Atmosfera</i>, "Global Climate Trends in Seven Climatic Parameters: A Comparative Analysis Across 100 Locations". While the topic of your manuscript is of relevance, there are many papers in the literature that report similar studies with more robust methodologies, and the results of your study are, in your own words, preliminary.</p> <p>In view of this, I regret to inform you that your manuscript has being rejected and will not be sent to external reviewers.</p> <p>Please note that this decision does not reflect on the merit of your study. I recommend you to make a more in-depth analysis of your selected climatic trends, including a more robust methodology, and to submit your reviewed work to a more appropriate journal where it can be assessed by relevant reviewers.</p>

Submissions to journals ended in May 2026 after 2.5 years.